

COMMON FIXED POINT THEOREMS IN COMPATIBLE MAPPINGS OF TYPE (P*) OF GENERALIZED INTUITIONISTIC FUZZY METRIC SPACES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we give some new definition of Compatible mappings of type (P), type (P-1) and type (P-2) in intuitionistic generalized fuzzy metric spaces and prove Common fixed point theorems for six mappings under the conditions of compatible mappings of type (P-1) and type (P-2) in complete intuitionistic fuzzy metric spaces. Our results intuitionistically fuzzify the result of Muthuraj and Pandiselvi [15]

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KEYWORDS

Intuitionistic fuzzy metric spaces, compatible mappings of type (P), type (P-1) and type (P-2) , common fixed point .

1.INTRODUCTION

The Concept of fuzzy set was introduced by Zadeh [23] in 1965 .Following the concept of fuzzy sets, Deng [6] Kaleva and Seikalla [12] and kramosil and Michalek [13] introduced the concept of fuzzy metric space, George and Veeramani [7] modified the concept of fuzzy metric space introduced by kramosil and Michalek [13] .

Further, Sedghi and Shobe [19] defined \mathcal{M} -fuzzy metric space and proved a common fixed point theorem in it. Jong Seo Park [15] introduced the concept of semi compatible and Weak Compatible maps in fuzzy metric space and proved some fixed point theorems satisfying certain conditions in \mathcal{M} -fuzzy metric spaces.

As a generalization of fuzzy sets, Atanassov [1] introduced and studied the concept of intuitionistic fuzzy sets. Using the idea of intuitionistic fuzzy sets Park [16] defined the notion of intuitionistic fuzzy metric space with the help of continuous t- norm and continuous t- conorm as a generalization of fuzzy metric space, George and Veeramani [8] had showed that every metric induces an intuitionistic fuzzy metric and found a necessary and sufficient conditions for an intuitionistic fuzzy metric space to be complete. Choudhary [4] introduced mutually contractive sequence of self maps and proved a fixed point theorem. Kramaosil and Michalek [13] introduced the notion of Cauchy sequences in an intuitionistic fuzzy metric space and proved the well known fixed point theorem of Banach[2]. Turkoglu et al [22] gave the generalization of Jungck's[11] Common fixed point theorem to intuitionistic fuzzy metric spaces.

In this paper, we extend the result of common fixed point theorem for compatible mappings of type (P-1) and type (P-2) in intuitionistic fuzzy metric space and prove common fixed point theorem of type (P-1) and type (P-2) in intuitionistic fuzzy metric spaces, we also give an example to validate our main theorem. Our results intuitionistically fuzzify the result of Muthuraj and Pandiselvi [15].

2. PRELIMINARIES

We start with the following definitions.

Definition 2.1

A binary operation $*$: $[0,1] \times [0,1] \rightarrow [0,1]$ is said to be a continuous t-norm if $*$ satisfies the following conditions.

- (i) $*$ is commutative and associative,
- (ii) $*$ is continuous,
- (iii) $a*1 = a$ for all $a \in [0,1]$,
- (iv) $a*b \leq c*d$ whenever $a \leq c$ and $b \leq d$ for all $a,b,c,d \in [0,1]$.

Definition 2.2

A binary operation \diamond : $[0,1] \times [0,1] \rightarrow [0,1]$ is said to be a continuous t-conorm if \diamond satisfies the following conditions :

- (i) \diamond is commutative and associative,
- (ii) \diamond is continuous,
- (iii) $a \diamond 0 = a$ for all $a \in [0,1]$,
- (iv) $a \diamond b \leq c \diamond d$ whenever $a \leq c$ and $b \leq d$ for all $a,b,c,d \in [0,1]$.

Definition 2.3

A 5-tuple $(X, \mathcal{M}, \mathcal{N}, *, \diamond)$ is called an intuitionistic fuzzy metric space if X is an arbitrary set, $*$ is a continuous t-norm, \diamond a continuous t-conorm and \mathcal{M}, \mathcal{N} are fuzzy sets on $X^3 \times (0, \infty)$, satisfying the following conditions, for each $x, y, z, a \in X$ and $t, s > 0$,

- a) $\mathcal{M}(x, y, z, t) + \mathcal{N}(x, y, z, t) \leq 1$.
- b) $\mathcal{M}(x, y, z, t) > 0$.
- c) $\mathcal{M}(x, y, z, t) = 1$ if and only if $x = y = z$.
- d) $\mathcal{M}(x, y, z, t) = \mathcal{M}(p\{x, y, z\}, t)$ where p is a permutation function,
- e) $\mathcal{M}(x, y, a, t) * \mathcal{M}(a, z, z, s) \leq \mathcal{M}(x, y, z, t + s)$
- f) $\mathcal{M}(x, y, z) : (0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is continuous
- g) $\mathcal{N}(x, y, z, t) > 0$
- h) $\mathcal{N}(x, y, z, t) = 0$, if and only if $x = y = z$,
- i) $\mathcal{N}(x, y, z, t) = \mathcal{N}(p\{x, y, z\}, t)$ where p is a permutation function,
- j) $\mathcal{N}(x, y, a, t) \diamond \mathcal{N}(a, z, z, s) \geq \mathcal{N}(x, y, z, t + s)$,
- k) $\mathcal{N}(x, y, z, \cdot) : (0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is continuous.

Then $(\mathcal{M}, \mathcal{N})$ is called an intuitionistic fuzzy metric on X .

Example 2.4

Let $X = \mathbb{R}$, and $\mathcal{M}(x, y, z, t) = \frac{t}{t+|x-y|+|y-z|+|z-x|}$, $\mathcal{N}(x, y, z, t) = \frac{|x-y|+|y-z|+|z-x|}{t+|x-y|+|y-z|+|z-x|}$ for every x, y, z and $t > 0$, let A and B defined as $Ax = 2x + 1$, $Bx = x + 2$, consider the sequence $x_n = \frac{1}{n} + 1$, $n = 1, 2, \dots$. Thus we have

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{M}(Ax_n, 3, 3, t) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{M}(Bx_n, 3, 3, t) = 1 \text{ and}$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{N}(Ax_n, 3, 3, t) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{N}(Bx_n, 3, 3, t) = 0, \text{ for every } t > 0.$$

Then A and B satisfying the property (E).

Definition 2.5

Let $(X, \mathcal{M}, \mathcal{N}, *, \diamond)$ be an intuitionistic fuzzy metric space and $\{x_n\}$ be a sequence in X .

- a) $\{x_n\}$ is said to be converges to a point $x \in X$, if $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{M}(x, x, x_n, t) = 1$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{N}(x, x, x_n, t) = 0$, for all $t > 0$.
- b) $\{x_n\}$ is called Cauchy sequence if $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{M}(x_{n+p}, x_{n+p}, x_n, t) = 1$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{N}(x_{n+p}, x_{n+p}, x_n, t) = 0$ for all $t > 0$ and $p > 0$.
- c) An intuitionistic fuzzy metric space in which every Cauchy sequence is convergent is said to be complete.

Lemma 2.6

Let $(X, \mathcal{M}, \mathcal{N}, *, \diamond)$ be an intuitionistic fuzzy metric space. Then $\mathcal{M}(x, y, z, t)$ and $\mathcal{N}(x, y, z, t)$ are non-decreasing with respect to t , for all x, y, z in X .

Proof

By definition 2.3, for each $x, y, z, a \in X$ and $t, s > 0$

we have $\mathcal{M}(x, y, a, t) * \mathcal{M}(a, z, z, s) \leq \mathcal{M}(x, y, z, t + s)$. If we set $a = z$,

we get $\mathcal{M}(z, y, z, t) * \mathcal{M}(z, z, z, s) \leq \mathcal{M}(x, y, z, t + s)$, that is

$$\mathcal{M}(x, y, z, t + s) \geq \mathcal{M}(x, y, z, t).$$

Similarly, $\mathcal{N}(x, y, a, t) \diamond \mathcal{N}(a, z, z, s) \geq \mathcal{N}(x, y, z, t + s)$, for each $x, y, z, a \in X$ and

$t, s > 0$, by definition of $(X, \mathcal{N}, \diamond)$. If we set $a = z$, we get

$$\mathcal{N}(x, y, z, t) \diamond \mathcal{N}(z, z, z, s) \geq \mathcal{N}(x, y, z, t + s)$$

that is $\mathcal{N}(x, y, z, t + s) \leq \mathcal{N}(x, y, z, t)$. Hence in IFMS $(X, \mathcal{M}, \mathcal{N}, *, \diamond)$,

$\mathcal{M}(x, y, z, t)$ and $\mathcal{N}(x, y, z, t)$ are non-decreasing with respect to t , for all x, y, z in X .

3.COMPATIBLE MAPPINGS OF TYPE

Definition 3.1

Let A and S be self mappings from an intuitionistic fuzzy metric space $(X, \mathcal{M}, \mathcal{N}, *, \diamond)$ into itself.

Then the mappings are said to be compatible if

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{M}(ASx_n, SAx_n, SAx_n, t) = 1 \text{ and}$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{N}(ASx_n, SAx_n, SAx_n, t) = 0, \text{ for all } t > 0 \text{ whenever } \{x_n\} \text{ is a sequence in } X \text{ such that } \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Ax_n$$

$$= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Sx_n = z \text{ for some } z \in X.$$

Definition 3.2

Let A and S be self mappings from an intuitionistic fuzzy metric space $(X, \mathcal{M}, \mathcal{N}, *, \diamond)$ into itself. Then the mappings are said to be compatible of type (P), if

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{M}(AAx_n, SSx_n, SSx_n, t) = 1 \text{ and } \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{N}(AAx_n, SSx_n, SSx_n, t) = 0 \text{ for all } t > 0, \text{ whenever}$$

$$\{x_n\} \text{ is a sequence in } X \text{ such that } \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Ax_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Sx_n = z \text{ for some } z \in X.$$

Definition 3.3

Let A and S be self mappings from an intuitionistic fuzzy metric space $(X, \mathcal{M}, \mathcal{N}, *, \diamond)$ into itself. Then the mappings are said to be R-Weakly commuting of type (P), if there exists some $R > 0$, such that $\mathcal{M}(AAx, SSx, SSx, t) \geq \mathcal{M}(Ax, Sx, Sx, \frac{t}{R})$,

$$\mathcal{N}(AAx, SSx, SSx, t) \leq \mathcal{N}(Ax, Sx, Sx, \frac{t}{R}), \text{ for all } x \text{ in } X \text{ and } t > 0.$$

Definition 3.4

Let A and S be self mappings from an intuitionistic fuzzy metric space $(X, \mathcal{M}, \mathcal{N}, *, \diamond)$ into itself. Then the mappings are said to be compatible of type (P-1) if

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{M}(SAx_n, AAx_n, AAx_n, t) = 1 \text{ and } \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{N}(SAx_n, AAx_n, AAx_n, t) = 0 \text{ for all } t > 0, \text{ whenever}$$

$$\{x_n\} \text{ is a sequence in } X \text{ such that } \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Ax_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Sx_n = z \text{ for some } z \in X.$$

Definition 3.5

Let A and S be self mappings from an intuitionistic fuzzy metric space $(X, \mathcal{M}, \mathcal{N}, *, \diamond)$ into itself. Then the mappings are said to be compatible of type (P-2) if

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{M}(AAx_n, SSx_n, SSx_n, t) = 1 \text{ and } \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{N}(AAx_n, SSx_n, SSx_n, t) = 0 \text{ for all } t > 0 \text{ whenever } \{x_n\}$$

$$\text{is a sequence in } X \text{ such that } \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Ax_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Sx_n = z \text{ for some } z \in X.$$

Proposition 3.6

Let A and S be self mappings from an intuitionistic fuzzy metric space $(X, \mathcal{M}, \mathcal{N}, *, \diamond)$ into itself.

- a) If A is continuous map then the pair of mappings (A, S) is compatible of type (P-1) if and only if A and S are compatible.
- b) If S is a continuous map then the pair of mappings (A, S) is compatible of type (P-2) if and only if A and S are compatible.

Proof

- a) Let $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Ax_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Sx_n = z$ for some $z \in X$, and let the pair (A, S) be compatible of type (P-1). Since A is continuous, we have $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} ASx_n = Az$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} AAx_n = Az$. Therefore it follows that

$$\mathcal{M}(SAx_n, ASx_n, ASx_n, t) \geq \mathcal{M}\left(SAx_n, AAx_n, AAx_n, \frac{t}{2}\right) * \mathcal{M}\left(AAx_n, ASx_n, ASx_n, \frac{t}{2}\right) \text{ and}$$

$$\mathcal{N}(SAx_n, ASx_n, ASx_n, t) \leq \mathcal{N}\left(SAx_n, AAx_n, AAx_n, \frac{t}{2}\right) \diamond \mathcal{N}\left(AAx_n, ASx_n, ASx_n, \frac{t}{2}\right)$$

yields $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{M}(SAx_n, ASx_n, ASx_n, t) \geq 1 * 1 = 1$ and

$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{N}(SAx_n, ASx_n, ASx_n, t) \leq 0 \diamond 0 = 0$ and so the mappings A and S are compatible.

Now, let A and S be compatible. Therefore it follows that

$$\mathcal{M}(SAx_n, AAx_n, AAx_n, t) \geq \mathcal{M}\left(SAx_n, ASx_n, ASx_n, \frac{t}{2}\right)$$

$$* \mathcal{M}\left(ASx_n, AAx_n, AAx_n, \frac{t}{2}\right)$$

$$\mathcal{N}(SAx_n, AAx_n, AAx_n, t) \leq \mathcal{N}\left(SAx_n, ASx_n, ASx_n, \frac{t}{2}\right)$$

$$\diamond \mathcal{N}\left(ASx_n, AAx_n, AAx_n, \frac{t}{2}\right)$$

yields $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{M}(SAx_n, AAx_n, AAx_n, t) \geq 1 * 1 = 1$ and

$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{N}(SAx_n, AAx_n, AAx_n, t) \leq 0 \diamond 0 = 0$ and

so that pair of mappings (A,S) are compatible of type (P-1).

- b) Let $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Sx_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Ax_n = z$ for some z in X and let the pair (A, S) be compatible of type (P-2). Since S is continuous, we have $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} SAx_n = Sz$ and

$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} SSx_n = Sz$. Therefore it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{M}(SAx_n, ASx_n, ASx_n, t) &\geq \mathcal{M}\left(SAx_n, SSx_n, SSx_n, \frac{t}{2}\right) \\ &* \mathcal{M}\left(SSx_n, ASx_n, ASx_n, \frac{t}{2}\right) \text{ and} \\ \mathcal{N}(SAx_n, ASx_n, ASx_n, t) &\leq \mathcal{N}\left(SAx_n, SSx_n, SSx_n, \frac{t}{2}\right) \\ &\diamond \mathcal{N}\left(SSx_n, ASx_n, ASx_n, \frac{t}{2}\right) \end{aligned}$$

yields $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{M}(SAx_n, ASx_n, ASx_n, t) \geq 1 * 1 = 1$ and

$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{N}(SAx_n, ASx_n, ASx_n, t) \leq 0 \diamond 0 = 0$ and so the mappings A and S are compatible.

Now let A and S be compatible. Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{M}(ASx_n, SSx_n, SSx_n, t) &\geq \mathcal{M}\left(ASx_n, SAx_n, SAx_n, \frac{t}{2}\right) \\ &* \mathcal{M}\left(SAx_n, SSx_n, SSx_n, \frac{t}{2}\right) \text{ and} \\ \mathcal{N}(ASx_n, SSx_n, SSx_n, t) &\leq \mathcal{N}\left(ASx_n, SAx_n, SAx_n, \frac{t}{2}\right) \\ &\diamond \mathcal{N}\left(SAx_n, SSx_n, SSx_n, \frac{t}{2}\right) \end{aligned}$$

yields $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{M}(ASx_n, SSx_n, SSx_n, t) \geq 1 * 1 = 1$ and

$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{N}(ASx_n, SSx_n, SSx_n, t) \leq 0 \diamond 0 = 0$ and so the pair of mappings (A, S) are compatible of type (P-2).

Proposition 3.7

Let A and S be self mappings from an intuitionistic fuzzy metric space $(X, \mathcal{M}, \mathcal{N}, *, \diamond)$ into itself. If the pair (A, S) is compatible of type (P-2) and $Sz = Az$ for some $z \in X$. Then $ASz = SSz$.

Proof:

Let $\{x_n\}$ be a sequence in X defined by $x_n = z$ for $n=1,2,\dots$ and let $Az = Sz$.

Then we have $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Sx_n = Sz$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Ax_n = Az$. Since the pair (A, S) is compatible of type (P-2),

we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{M}(ASz, SSz, SSz, t) &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{M}(ASx_n, SSx_n, SSx_n, t) = 1 \text{ and} \\ \mathcal{N}(ASz, SSz, SSz, t) &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{N}(ASx_n, SSx_n, SSx_n, t) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $ASz = SSz$.

Proposition 3.8

Let A and S self mappings from an intuitionistic fuzzy metric space $(X, \mathcal{M}, \mathcal{N}, *, \diamond)$ with $t * t \geq t$ and $(1-t) \diamond (1-t) \leq 1-t$ for all $t \in [0, 1]$ if the pair (A, S) are compatible of type (p -1) and $Ax_n, Sx_n \rightarrow z$ for some z in X and a sequence $\{x_n\}$ in X.

Then $AAx_n \rightarrow Sz$, if S is continuous at z.

Proof

Since S is continuous at z, we have $Sx_n \rightarrow Sz$. Since the pair (A, S) are compatible of type (P-1), we have $\mathcal{M}(SAx_n, AAx_n, AAx_n, t) \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. It follows that

$$\mathcal{M}(Sz, AAx_n, AAx_n, t) \geq \mathcal{M}(Sz, SAx_n, SAx_n, \frac{t}{2}) * \mathcal{M}(SAx_n, AAx_n, AAx_n, \frac{t}{2}) \text{ and}$$

$$\mathcal{N}(Sz, AAx_n, AAx_n, t) \leq \mathcal{N}(Sz, SAx_n, SAx_n, \frac{t}{2}) * \mathcal{N}(SAx_n, AAx_n, AAx_n, \frac{t}{2}) \text{ yield}$$

$$\mathcal{M}(Sz, AAx_n, AAx_n, t) \geq 1 * 1 = 1 \text{ and}$$

$$\mathcal{N}(Sz, AAx_n, AAx_n, t) \leq 0 \diamond 0 = 0 \text{ and so}$$

we have $AAx_n \rightarrow Sz$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Proposition 3.9

Let A and S be self mappings from an intuitionistic fuzzy metric space $(X, \mathcal{M}, \mathcal{N}, *, \diamond)$ with $t * t \geq t$ and $(1-t) \diamond (1-t) \leq 1-t$ for $t \in [0, 1]$. If the pair (A, S) are compatible of type (P - 2) and $Ax_n, Sx_n \rightarrow z$ for some z in X and sequence $\{x_n\}$ in X. Then $SSx_n \rightarrow Az$ if A is continuous at z.

Proof

Since A is continuous at z, we have $ASx_n \rightarrow Az$. Since the pair (A, S) are compatible of type (P - 2), we have $\mathcal{M}(ASx_n, SSx_n, SSx_n, t) \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, it follows that

$$\mathcal{M}(Az, SSx_n, SSx_n, t) \geq \mathcal{M}(Az, ASx_n, ASx_n, \frac{t}{2}) * \mathcal{M}(ASx_n, SSx_n, SSx_n, \frac{t}{2}) \text{ and}$$

$$\mathcal{N}(Az, SSx_n, SSx_n, t) \leq \mathcal{N}(Az, ASx_n, ASx_n, \frac{t}{2}) \diamond \mathcal{N}(ASx_n, SSx_n, SSx_n, \frac{t}{2}) \text{ yield}$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{M}(Az, SSx_n, SSx_n, t) \geq 1 * 1 = 1 \text{ and}$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{N}(Az, SSx_n, SSx_n, t) \leq 0 \diamond 0 = 0 \text{ and so}$$

we have $SSx_n \rightarrow Az$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

4. MAIN RESULTS

Theorem 4.1

Let $(X, \mathcal{M}, \mathcal{N}, *, \diamond)$ be a complete generalized intuitionistic fuzzy metric space and let A, B, P, Q, S and T be self mappings of X satisfying the following conditions.

- (i) $P(X) \subseteq ST(X), Q(X) \subseteq AB(X)$
- (ii) The pair (P, AB) and (Q, ST) are compatible mappings of type (P)
- (iii) ST is continuous
- (iv) $\mathcal{M}(Px, Qz, Qz, qt) \geq \min \{ \mathcal{M}(ABx, Py, Qy, t), \mathcal{M}(ABx, Py, STz, t), \mathcal{M}(Qy, STz, Py, t), \mathcal{M}(ABx, Qy, STz, t) \}$ and
 $\mathcal{N}(Px, Qz, Qz, qt) \leq \max \{ \mathcal{N}(ABx, Py, Qy, t), \mathcal{N}(ABx, Py, STz, t), \mathcal{N}(Qy, STz, Py, t), \mathcal{N}(ABx, Qy, STz, t) \}$

then the mappings P, Q, AB and ST have a unique common fixed point in X .

Proof

Let x_0 be any arbitrary point in X . Thus we construct a sequence $\{y_n\}$ in X such that $y_{2n-1} = STx_{2n-1} = Px_{2n-2}$ and $y_{2n} = ABx_{2n} = Qx_{2n-1}$. Put $x = x_{2n-1}, y = x_{2n-1}, z = x_{2n}$.

$$\mathcal{M}(Px_{2n-1}, Qx_{2n}, Qx_{2n}, qt) \geq \min \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathcal{M}(ABx_{2n-1}, Px_{2n-1}, Qx_{2n-1}, t), \\ \mathcal{M}(ABx_{2n-1}, Px_{2n-1}, STx_{2n}, t), \\ \mathcal{M}(Qx_{2n-1}, STx_{2n}, Px_{2n-1}, t), \\ \mathcal{M}(ABx_{2n-1}, Qx_{2n-1}, STx_{2n}, t) \end{array} \right\}$$

$$\mathcal{M}(y_{2n}, y_{2n+1}, y_{2n+1}, qt) \geq \min \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathcal{M}(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n}, y_{2n}, t), \\ \mathcal{M}(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n}, y_{2n}, t), \\ \mathcal{M}(y_{2n}, y_{2n}, y_{2n}, t), \\ \mathcal{M}(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n}, y_{2n}, t) \end{array} \right\}$$

$$\mathcal{M}(y_{2n}, y_{2n+1}, y_{2n+1}, qt) \geq \mathcal{M}(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n}, y_{2n}, t)$$

This implies that $\mathcal{M}(y_{2n}, y_{2n+1}, y_{2n+1}, t)$ is an increasing sequence of positive real numbers.

$$\mathcal{N}(Px_{2n-1}, Qx_{2n}, Qx_{2n}, qt) \leq \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathcal{N}(ABx_{2n-1}, Px_{2n-1}, Qx_{2n-1}, t), \\ \mathcal{N}(ABx_{2n-1}, Px_{2n-1}, STx_{2n}, t), \\ \mathcal{N}(Qx_{2n-1}, STx_{2n}, Px_{2n-1}, t), \\ \mathcal{N}(ABx_{2n-1}, Qx_{2n-1}, STx_{2n}, t) \end{array} \right\}$$

$$\mathcal{N}(y_{2n}, y_{2n+1}, y_{2n+1}, qt) \leq \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathcal{N}(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n}, y_{2n}, t), \\ \mathcal{N}(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n}, y_{2n}, t), \\ \mathcal{N}(y_{2n}, y_{2n}, y_{2n}, t), \\ \mathcal{N}(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n}, y_{2n}, t) \end{array} \right\}$$

$$\mathcal{N}(y_{2n}, y_{2n+1}, y_{2n+1}, qt) \leq \mathcal{N}(y_{2n-1}, y_{2n}, y_{2n}, t)$$

This implies that $\mathcal{N}(y_{2n}, y_{2n+1}, y_{2n+1}, t)$ is an decreasing sequence of positive real numbers.

Now to prove that $\mathcal{M}(y_n, y_{n+1}, y_{n+1}, t)$ converges to 1 as $n \rightarrow \infty$ and

$\mathcal{N}(y_{2n}, y_{2n+1}, y_{2n+1}, t)$ converges to 0 as $n \rightarrow \infty$. By lemma 2.6,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{M}(y_n, y_{n+1}, y_{n+1}, t) &\geq \mathcal{M}\left(y_{n-1}, y_n, y_n, \frac{t}{q}\right) \geq \mathcal{M}\left(y_{n-2}, y_{n-1}, y_{n-1}, \frac{t}{q^2}\right) \\ &\dots \geq \mathcal{M}\left(y_0, y_1, y_1, \frac{t}{q^n}\right) \end{aligned}$$

Thus $\mathcal{M}(y_n, y_{n+1}, y_{n+1}, t) \geq \mathcal{M}\left(y_0, y_1, y_1, \frac{t}{q^n}\right)$ and

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{N}(y_n, y_{n+1}, y_{n+1}, t) &\leq \mathcal{N}\left(y_{n-1}, y_n, y_n, \frac{t}{q}\right) \leq \mathcal{N}\left(y_{n-2}, y_{n-1}, y_{n-1}, \frac{t}{q^2}\right) \\ &\dots \leq \mathcal{N}\left(y_0, y_1, y_1, \frac{t}{q^n}\right) \end{aligned}$$

Then by the definition of IFMS,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{M}(y_n, y_{n+p}, y_{n+p}, t) &\geq \mathcal{M}(y_n, y_{n+1}, y_{n+1}, \frac{t}{p}) * \dots p \text{ times} \dots * \mathcal{M}(y_{n+p-1}, y_{n+p}, y_{n+p}, \frac{t}{p}) \\ &\geq \mathcal{M}(y_0, y_1, y_1, \frac{t}{q^n}) * \dots p \text{ times} \dots * \mathcal{M}(y_0, y_1, y_1, \frac{t}{pq^{n+p-1}}) \end{aligned}$$

Thus by the definition of IFMS,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{N}(y_n, y_{n+p}, y_{n+p}, t) &\leq \mathcal{N}(y_n, y_{n+1}, y_{n+1}, \frac{t}{p}) * \dots p \text{ times} \dots * \mathcal{N}(y_{n+p-1}, y_{n+p}, y_{n+p}, \frac{t}{p}) \\ &\leq \mathcal{N}(y_0, y_1, y_1, \frac{t}{q^n}) * \dots p \text{ times} \dots * \mathcal{N}(y_0, y_1, y_1, \frac{t}{pq^{n+p-1}}). \end{aligned}$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{M}(y_n, y_{n+p}, y_{n+p}, t) \geq 1 * 1 * \dots p \text{ times} \dots * 1. \quad \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{M}(y_n, y_{n+p}, y_{n+p}, t) = 1 \text{ and}$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{N}(y_n, y_{n+p}, y_{n+p}, t) \leq 0 * 0 * \dots p \text{ times} \dots * 0. \quad \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{N}(y_n, y_{n+p}, y_{n+p}, t) = 0.$$

Thus $\{y_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in intuitionistic fuzzy metric space X .

Since X is complete, there exists a point $u \in X$ such that $y_n \rightarrow u$.

Thus $\{ABx_{2n}\}, \{Qx_{2n-1}\}, \{STx_{2n-1}\}, \{Px_{2n-2}\}$ are Cauchy sequence converge to u .

Put $x = ABx_{2n}, y = u, z = STx_{2n-1}$ in (iv), we get

$$\mathcal{M}(PABx_{2n}, QSTx_{2n-1}, QSTx_{2n-1}, qt) \geq \min \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathcal{M}(ABABx_{2n}, Pu, Qu, t), \\ \mathcal{M}(ABABx_{2n}, Pu, STSTx_{2n-1}, t), \\ \mathcal{M}(Qu, STSTx_{2n-1}, Pu, t), \\ \mathcal{M}(ABABx_{2n}, Qu, STSTx_{2n-1}, t), \end{array} \right\} \text{ and}$$

$$\mathcal{N}(PABx_{2n}, QSTx_{2n-1}, QSTx_{2n-1}, qt) \leq \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathcal{N}(ABABx_{2n}, Pu, Qu, t), \\ \mathcal{N}(ABABx_{2n}, Pu, STSTx_{2n-1}, t), \\ \mathcal{N}(Qu, STSTx_{2n-1}, Pu, t), \\ \mathcal{N}(ABABx_{2n}, Qu, STSTx_{2n-1}, t), \end{array} \right\}.$$

Now take the limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$ and using (ii), we get,

$$\mathcal{M}(Pu, Qu, Qu, qt) \geq \min \left\{ \mathcal{M}(Pu, Pu, Qu, t), \mathcal{M}(Pu, Pu, Qu, t) \right\} \text{ and}$$

$$\mathcal{M}(Qu, Qu, Pu, t), \mathcal{M}(Pu, Qu, Qu, t)$$

$$\mathcal{N}(Pu, Qu, Qu, qt) \leq \max \left\{ \mathcal{N}(Pu, Pu, Qu, t), \mathcal{N}(Pu, Pu, Qu, t) \right\}$$

$$\mathcal{N}(Qu, Qu, Pu, t), \mathcal{N}(Pu, Qu, Qu, t)$$

Then by lemma 2.6, we get

$$\mathcal{M}(Pu, Qu, Qu, qt) \geq \mathcal{M}(Pu, Qu, Qu, t) \text{ and}$$

$$\mathcal{N}(Pu, Qu, Qu, qt) \leq \mathcal{N}(Pu, Qu, Qu, t).$$

Therefore $Pu = Qu$. Now put $x = ABx_{2n}$, $y = x_{2n-1}$, $z = x_{2n-1}$, in (iv), we get

$$\mathcal{M}(PABx_{2n}, Qx_{2n-1}, Qx_{2n-1}, qt) \geq \min \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathcal{M}(ABABx_{2n}, Px_{2n-1}, Qx_{2n-1}, t), \\ \mathcal{M}(ABABx_{2n}, Px_{2n-1}, STx_{2n-1}, t), \\ \mathcal{M}(Qx_{2n-1}, STx_{2n-1}, Px_{2n-1}, t), \\ \mathcal{M}(ABABx_{2n}, Qx_{2n-1}, STx_{2n-1}, t) \end{array} \right\} \text{ and}$$

$$\mathcal{N}(PABx_{2n}, Qx_{2n-1}, Qx_{2n-1}, qt) \leq \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathcal{N}(ABABx_{2n}, Px_{2n-1}, Qx_{2n-1}, t), \\ \mathcal{N}(ABABx_{2n}, Px_{2n-1}, STx_{2n-1}, t), \\ \mathcal{N}(Qx_{2n-1}, STx_{2n-1}, Px_{2n-1}, t), \\ \mathcal{N}(ABABx_{2n}, Qx_{2n-1}, STx_{2n-1}, t) \end{array} \right\}$$

Thus we have $\mathcal{M}(Pu, u, u, qt) \geq \mathcal{M}(Pu, u, u, t)$ and

$$\mathcal{N}(Pu, u, u, qt) \leq \mathcal{N}(Pu, u, u, t).$$

Therefore $Pu = u$. This implies $Pu = Qu = u$.

Now put $x = Px_{2n-2}$, $y = Px_{2n-2}$, $z = u$ in (iv), we get

$$\mathcal{M}(PPx_{2n-2}, Qu, Qu, qt) \geq \min \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathcal{M}(ABPx_{2n-2}, PPx_{2n-2}, QPx_{2n-2}, t), \\ \mathcal{M}(ABPx_{2n-2}, PPx_{2n-2}, STu, t), \\ \mathcal{M}(QPx_{2n-2}, STu, PPx_{2n-2}, t), \\ \mathcal{M}(ABPx_{2n-2}, QPx_{2n-2}, STu, t) \end{array} \right\} \text{ and}$$

$$\mathcal{N}(PPx_{2n-2}, Qu, Qu, qt) \leq \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathcal{M}(ABPx_{2n-2}, PPx_{2n-2}, QPx_{2n-2}, t), \\ \mathcal{M}(ABPx_{2n-2}, PPx_{2n-2}, STu, t), \\ \mathcal{M}(QPx_{2n-2}, STu, PPx_{2n-2}, t), \\ \mathcal{M}(ABPx_{2n-2}, QPx_{2n-2}, STu, t) \end{array} \right\}.$$

Now taking the limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$ and on using (ii) and (iii), we get

$$\mathcal{M}(ABu, u, u, qt) \geq \min \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathcal{M}(ABu, ABu, u, t), \quad \mathcal{M}(ABu, ABu, u, t), \\ \mathcal{M}(Qu, u, ABu, t), \quad \mathcal{M}(ABu, Qu, u, t) \end{array} \right\}$$

$$\mathcal{N}(ABu, u, u, qt) \leq \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathcal{N}(ABu, ABu, u, t), \quad \mathcal{N}(ABu, ABu, u, t), \\ \mathcal{N}(Qu, u, ABu, t), \quad \mathcal{N}(ABu, Qu, u, t) \end{array} \right\}.$$

This implies

$$\mathcal{M}(ABu, u, u, qt) \geq \min \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathcal{M}(ABu, ABu, u, t), \quad \mathcal{M}(ABu, ABu, u, t), \\ \mathcal{M}(u, u, ABu, t), \quad \mathcal{M}(ABu, u, u, t) \end{array} \right\}$$

$$\mathcal{N}(ABu, u, u, qt) \leq \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathcal{N}(ABu, ABu, u, t), \quad \mathcal{N}(ABu, ABu, u, t), \\ \mathcal{N}(u, u, ABu, t), \quad \mathcal{N}(ABu, u, u, t) \end{array} \right\}.$$

Therefore by lemma (2.6) we have $ABu = u$. Thus $Pu = Qu = ABu = u$.

Put $x = u, y = u, z = Qx_{2n-1}$, in (iv) we get

$$\mathcal{M}(Pu, QQx_{2n-1}, QQx_{2n-1}, qt) \geq \min \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathcal{M}(u, u, u, t), \quad \mathcal{M}(u, u, STu, t), \\ \mathcal{M}(u, STu, u, t), \quad \mathcal{M}(u, u, STu, t) \end{array} \right\}$$

$$\mathcal{N}(Pu, QQx_{2n-1}, QQx_{2n-1}, qt) \leq \max \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathcal{N}(u, u, u, t), \quad \mathcal{N}(u, u, STu, t), \\ \mathcal{N}(u, STu, u, t), \quad \mathcal{N}(u, u, STu, t) \end{array} \right\}.$$

On using lemma, (2.6) we have

$$\mathcal{M}(STu, STu, u, qt) \geq \mathcal{M}(STu, STu, u, t) \text{ and}$$

$$\mathcal{M}(STu, STu, u, qt) \geq \mathcal{M}(STu, STu, u, t)$$

$$\mathcal{N}(STu, STu, u, qt) \leq \mathcal{N}(STu, STu, u, t).$$

Thus $STu = u$. We get $Pu = Qu = ABu = STu = u$.

Uniqueness

Let w be another common fixed point of A, B, P, Q, S and T . Then

$$\mathcal{M}(Pu, Qw, Qw, qt) \geq \min \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathcal{M}(ABu, Pw, Qw, t), \quad \mathcal{M}(ABu, Pw, STw, t), \\ \mathcal{M}(Qw, STw, Pw, t), \quad \mathcal{M}(ABu, Qw, STw, t) \end{array} \right\}$$

$$\mathcal{M}(u, w, w, qt) \geq \min \left\{ \mathcal{M}(u, w, w, t), \mathcal{M}(u, w, w, t), \right. \\ \left. \mathcal{M}(w, w, w, t), \mathcal{M}(u, w, w, t) \right\}$$

$$\mathcal{M}(u, w, w, qt) \geq \mathcal{M}(u, w, w, t) \text{ and}$$

$$\mathcal{N}(Pu, Qw, Qw, qt) \leq \max \left\{ \mathcal{N}(ABu, Pw, Qw, t), \mathcal{N}(ABu, Pw, STw, t), \right. \\ \left. \mathcal{N}(Qw, STw, Pw, t), \mathcal{N}(ABu, Qw, STw, t) \right\}$$

$$\mathcal{N}(u, w, w, qt) \leq \max \left\{ \mathcal{N}(u, w, w, t), \mathcal{N}(u, w, w, t), \right. \\ \left. \mathcal{N}(w, w, w, t), \mathcal{N}(u, w, w, t) \right\} \mathcal{N}(u, w, w, qt) \leq \mathcal{N}(u, w, w, t),$$

which is a contradiction. Therefore $u = w$.

Hence the common fixed point is unique.

Corollary 4.2

Let $(X, \mathcal{M}, \mathcal{N}, *, \diamond)$ be a complete generalized intuitionistic fuzzy metric space and let A, P, Q and S be self mappings of X satisfying the following conditions.

- (i) $P(X) \subseteq S(X), Q(X) \subseteq A(X)$
- (ii) The pair (P, A) and (Q, S) are compatible mappings of type (P)
- (iii) S is continuous
- (iv) $\mathcal{M}(Px, Qz, Qz, qt) \geq \min \{ \mathcal{M}(Ax, Py, Qy, t), \mathcal{M}(Ax, Py, Sz, t), \\ \mathcal{M}(Qy, Sz, Py, t), \mathcal{M}(Ax, Qy, Sz, t) \}$ and
 $\mathcal{N}(Px, Qz, Qz, qt) \leq \max \{ \mathcal{N}(Ax, Py, Qy, t), \mathcal{N}(Ax, Py, Sz, t), \\ \mathcal{N}(Qy, Sz, Py, t), \mathcal{N}(Ax, Qy, Sz, t) \}.$

Then the mappings P, Q, A and S have a unique common fixed point in X .

Corollary 4.3

Let $(X, \mathcal{M}, \mathcal{N}, *, \diamond)$ be a complete generalized intuitionistic fuzzy metric space and let B, P, Q and T be self mappings of X satisfying the conditions (i), (ii), (iii), & (iv) with $S = I$ and $A = I$; Then the mappings B, P, Q and T have a unique common fixed point.

Corollary 4.4

Let $(X, \mathcal{M}, \mathcal{N}, *, \diamond)$ be a complete generalized intuitionistic fuzzy metric space and let A, B, P, Q, S and T be self mappings of X satisfying the following conditions:

- (i) $P(X) \subseteq ST(X), Q(X) \subseteq AB(X)$
- (ii) The pair (P, AB) and (Q, ST) are compatible mappings of type (P)
- (iii) ST is continuous
- (iv) $\mathcal{M}(Px, Qz, Qz, qt) \geq \mathcal{M}(ABx, Py, Qy, t) * \mathcal{M}(ABx, Py, STz, t) * \\ \mathcal{M}(Qy, STz, Py, t) * \mathcal{M}(ABx, Qy, STz, t)$ and
 $\mathcal{N}(Px, Qz, Qz, qt) \leq \mathcal{N}(ABx, Py, Qy, t) \diamond \mathcal{N}(ABx, Py, STz, t) \diamond \\ \mathcal{N}(Qy, STz, Py, t) \diamond \mathcal{N}(ABx, Qy, STz, t)$

Then the mappings P, Q, AB and ST have a unique common fixed point in X .

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